

Abstract

Acupuncture and Traditional Chinese Medicine: A Promising Complementary Approach for Depression.

EMA SIMÕES CALÇADA^{1*} .

¹ ABS – Health Level, Atlântico Business School, Vila Nova de Gaia, Porto, Portugal.

² IPB - Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (Polytechnic University of Bragança), Bragança, Portugal.

* Correspondence: ema.fsc@gmail.com

Abstract

Depression remains one of the most widespread mental health disorders globally and while numerous treatments exist, their effectiveness can vary. This has spurred a growing interest in alternative and complementary therapies, with acupuncture gaining significant attention.

This systematic review investigates the impact of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and acupuncture in managing depression. We analyzed 16 studies published between 2015 and 2024, retrieved from PubMed and ScienceDirect.

Our findings indicate that TCM and acupuncture can positively reduce depressive symptoms, serving as an effective therapeutic intervention. They can be used as a standalone treatment or as a complementary approach alongside conventional Western pharmacological therapy. Based on these results, we conclude that TCM and acupuncture offer a beneficial and side-effect-free option in the treatment of depression.

Keywords: Depression; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture; Treatment.

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